

TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE WITH SONGS

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Annotation: The article highlights the mechanisms of music and songs` influence on students` motivation, better acquiring of new material, developing of speech skills, creative and cognitive abilities and lowering the affective filter while teaching a foreign language.

Key words: teaching a foreign language, songs, motivation, affective filter.

Knowledge of foreign languages is a prerequisite for professional training of a specialist at a technical university. However, teaching experience shows that the level of foreign language proficiency of a number of students currently insufficient and requires constant attention. The main reason for the low academic performance of such students is low motivation, lack of significant incentives for learning a foreign language. On the other hand, students whose motivation to study this subject is high face psychological barriers in mastering foreign language, due, in particular, to different levels of pre-university training, as well as differences in social conditions, which are especially pronounced in large groups. The method of teaching a foreign language with the help of songs considered in the article reduces the degree of emotional tension, promotes more effective assimilation of educational material and increases motivation to learn a foreign language. Famous translator and psycholinguist D.N. Petrov claims that the reason for most problems with learning a foreign language are psychological blocks. "The first thing I ask pessimists is: "Where is it difficult for you when you say, show me?" Everyone shows the same points: throat ("I know everything, but I can't say"), stomach ("I'm afraid they will

laugh at mistakes") and forehead ("it's hard to compose a phrase, I can't put the words together").

The first step is to remove these blocks. After all, when we speak Russian, regardless of the level of education, we are not afraid of mistakes. And there are no physical difficulties" [1]. In addition, "words contain only 10-15% of the meaning, everything else is an emotional cloud that swirls around. When you strain and catch every word you see only these individual words: understandable incomprehensible and misunderstood. But if the vision is defocused, the overall picture becomes visible, and the thought reaches the addressee"

According to Stephen Krashen, the main obstacle to learning a foreign language is an "emotional filter" – a mental block caused by emotional factors. The formation of an emotional filter can be caused by factors such as motivation, self-confidence, anxiety.

Thus, students with high motivation, a high level of self-confidence and a low level of anxiety are more successful in mastering a foreign language. Indeed, from personal conversations with students, we learn that some of them find it difficult to speak a foreign language in the presence of stronger students, and they prefer to remain silent in class for fear of making a mistake and causing classmates to laugh.

Thus, creating an emotionally comfortable atmosphere in the classroom is the main condition for successful work. As N.H. Miftakhova notes, "the state of relaxation, natural or artificial, ... makes it possible to significantly intensify the assimilation of educational material ... For foreign language learners, this problem is extremely important, since language acquisition is largely associated with the problem of memory. Consciousness must be freed from rough work, it should be occupied with communication".

Speaking about erroneous stereotypes in the methodology of teaching foreign languages, N.H. Miftakhova notes that "the most common and fundamentally unacceptable disadvantage is ignoring the laws of step-by-step formation of knowledge, teachings and skills, and the psychology of their assimilation." In her opinion, the "formula of the cognitive process, obeying the dialectical law of

development: from the level of acquaintance to the level of abstract" should be applied to the study of a foreign language understanding to the level of practical use" In particular, N.H. Miftakhova calls the first stage of the educational process the stage of sensory cognition. "At the initial stage ...it is necessary to initiate interested participation or complicity in the process of receiving information.

In other words, the reliance on sensory perception should prevail here...It is recommended to achieve emotional coloring and saturation of both the source of information and the method of its presentation".

It seems to us that a great help in creating an emotionally comfortable working state and in forming a stable interest songs in a foreign language may be relevant to the subject.

The practical use of songs in foreign language lessons is not a new technique.

But for most teachers, the presence of music in the classroom seems to be something frivolous, distracting from studying. However, this is not the case. Music, songs in the classroom can become good helpers, provided competent, careful selection of material, its systematic use.

It is known that the more sensory organs are involved in the learning process, the more effective it is. Music, songs are a powerful tool teaching a foreign language. Language, like music, has a certain structure, rules. Words and notes are arranged into phrases and sentences, where there is rhythm, size, rhyme. Music in the classroom inspires, relaxes, captivates, adjusts to a subtle but strong wave of perception. In addition, music develops memory and thinking.

It has been proven that people who love music usually easily learn a foreign language. After all, any language is, first of all, a combination of sounds, a melody, a song. The ability to speak a foreign language largely depends on the ability to listen, hear and imitate. Musically a trained ear is a great help in mastering the language. If a person who has decided to learn a foreign language likes its sound, then the chances of learning this language and speaking it himself are very high. "I like how it sounds"; "beautiful"; "pleasant to listen to" – all these are verbally

expressed emotional prerequisites (often unconscious) that prepare the ground for a conscious learning process language.

T.M. Veselova and her colleagues note that songs in the studied foreign language have a positive effect on the process of perception and assimilation of language material by students: "Rhythm and rhyme allow using poetic texts not only as a memorable illustration of a linguistic phenomenon, but also an effective exercise involving repetition of sounds, words, parts of sentences, grammatical constructions.

Lexico-grammatical constructions, pronounced in a certain rhythm and accompanied by a musical background, cause positive emotions, are easier to assimilate and they are remembered for a long time". This conclusion was made by the authors of the textbook "Sing and learn English grammar" on the basis of a long-term study of the influence of musical and poetic rhythm on the formation of communication skills. The advantages of using songs in foreign language classes are well-founded.

For example, Daniel Kramer of Harvard University notes that "unlike dictation or substitution exercises divorced from reality, songs with their structure similar to a small story contain a consistent context, more suitable for understanding words". Moreover, songs, especially folk songs, reveal to students various social and historical aspects of the language being studied, introduce samples of folk wisdom.

Listening to songs performed by native speakers contributes to the correct pronunciation and training of perception and understanding of the text by ear.

Songs offer a variety of mnemonic codes, such as repetition, rhyme and melody, which help better memorization. Integration of songs of the studied language into fragments of the lesson devoted to grammar, significantly increases the ability of students to recall certain rules. Carefully selected songs are used not only for the introduction, training and consolidation of grammatical and lexical material, but also for the construction of monologue statements and discussions about the ideas or events touched upon in the song.

Unlike exercises that fly out of your head as soon as the lesson is over, songs can accompany students all their lives and become part of their culture. The opportunity to get acquainted in class on the example of a song with a new phenomenon, to understand, remember it and "take it with you" inspires students, increases their self-confidence, and nurturing success is the best way to motivate them to further study.

As S.D. Pivkin and N.S. Valeeva note, "motivation of educational and professional activity in teaching a foreign language is extremely important for the construction of educational work and determines its dynamics and ability to develop and improve not only the learning system, but also the language personality of the student as a future specialist, because it (motivation) is that mechanism, which sets the energy, direction and stability of her speech behavior". Songs in a foreign language lesson are addressed to bimodal learning (music is processed in the right hemisphere of the brain, and speech is processed in the left) and have a positive impact on the development of cognitive abilities of students. Finally, joint performance, choral singing relieves emotional tension, helps to strengthen interpersonal relationships and group cohesion.

In working with songs, we follow the methodology proposed by D. Kramer, who defines three basic steps of integrating music into the teaching of foreign languages:

- 1) approval of criteria for the selection of songs;
- 2) annotation
of lyrics;
- 3) work with the text:

Approval of criteria for the selection of songs.

When choosing songs, it is important to take into account the preferences of students and, at the same time, expand their horizons, cultivate a good musical taste. As for the criteria themselves, they are as follows:

- the lyrics of the song should correspond to the level of students, it should not be too difficult;

- the text should emphasize a certain question or topic of grammar;
- the diction of the performer should be clear so that students can easily understand the words.

Annotating song lyrics. The next step after choosing a song is annotating the text, i.e. removing possible lexical and grammatical difficulties that interfere with perception and understanding. For some songs, this means the interpretation of new words; for others, a literary translation of the original text. This stage may include the presentation of a brief biography of the composer, poet and performers, as well as events related to the history of the creation of the song.

Working with text. After selecting a song and preparing the audience for its perception, the stage of practical work begins. Some songs seem to be specially written for practicing grammar, others allow you to move from linguistic phenomena to speech.

Here are some examples of working with English-language songs.

The song "Let It Be" by The Beatles, for example, we use to train the verb tenses Present Simple Tense and Present Continuous Tense (present simple and present extended tense). In particular, we draw the attention of students to the presence of the ending –s in the verbs "comes", "shines", to its absence in the verbs "find", "agree", "wake up" and give the task to formulate the appropriate rule. Then, if necessary, we repeat the conjugation of the verb "to be" and find its personal forms in the text. Then we work on the vocabulary – we introduce and consolidate new lexical units, for example, such as "trouble" ("trouble"), "wisdom" ("wisdom"), explain the meaning of the phrase "broken hearted people" ("people with broken hearts"), figurative meanings of phrases "hour of darkness", "there is still a light that shines on me". We draw students' attention to the pronunciation of a specific English sound [a] occurring in the words "mother", "they", "though", "there", "the". Thus, only on this one song we are working on all aspects of the language – grammar, vocabulary, phonetics.

Music, songs play a huge role in our lives. They always accompany us to we didn't. Singing songs is natural. Learning a foreign language with the help of songs

is a natural, and, therefore, a convenient and successful way of learning a new culture, another, unknown until the world.

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